

The Coupling Constants Series and Interference – 8 Theory

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Abstract:

By analyzing the new framework of the 8-theory, which regard bosons as net curvature on a Lorentz manifold, invoked stationary by EL operator, and supported by the coupling constants series, it is possible to create a new model of the phenomena of interference. Analysis of that phenomenon will be presented alongside a visual model, with emphasis on interfacing distinct curvatures causing a mutual cancelation.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.12)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.13)$$

The image above represent a net curvature on the Lorentz manifold, in that specific case, it's the photon associated with $N_V = (+5)$ net variations, and total 128 variations. Suppose that we perform the two slits experiment and open an additional route for net curvature. this is the visualization of what could happen according to our new theory:

There are two ways to explain. The first is to say that two opposite but similar in magnitude curvature occupying the same space will have a segment of mutual cancelation. If we define ripple operators \wp from a starting area to another area, the mutual area of both will be the amount of interference.

$$\wp: A \rightarrow B \quad (1.131)$$

$$\wp: A' \rightarrow B \quad (1.132)$$

Interference will accrue at the manifold segment that is mutual to both starting point. Define the interference operator:

$$\approx: A \cap A' \quad (1.133)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)